

SCHOOL LEADERSHIP THROUGH THE LENS OF WOMEN SCHOOL HEADS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore on the lived experiences of women school heads of Ormoc City Division, Ormoc City District Eight on how they lead an institution. The study employed four (4) women school heads from Ormoc City Division - Eighth District regardless of the years they have served in the Department of Education (DepEd). Methodology utilized in the study included one-on-one semi-structured interview. The data were gathered through the use of semi-structured interview and were analyzed using the Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. Specifically, the study sought to answer what are the experiences of women school heads in school leadership. Based from the result of this study, the following sub-themes have been generated. First, the ambivalent emotions wherein they often discussed their mixed emotions based on their experiences in leading a school. Second, the equality in the workplace. Third, the stakeholders' partnership in leadership. Challenges were also encountered that aggravated participants' situation which agreed with the Leadership Labyrinth Theory. However, these women school heads have identified strategies on handling different situations in the school they are leading. The challenges that women school heads have experienced made them even wiser and stronger school heads. Based on the results of this study, it is recommended to increase the number of participants to investigate the influence of culture on the management of female school heads. Hence, explore the real experiences of women school heads in different cultures. A comparative study of men and women school heads' lived experiences is also recommended.

Keywords: *Lived Experiences, Women School Heads, School Leadership, Challenges*

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INTRODUCTION

Leadership is encouraging people to act toward a goal. Effective leaders inspire their followers to take positive action and have developed their skills. Research shows that school administrators influence students' academic performance second only to teachers (UNESCO, 2018; VVOB, 2018). According to Robinson et al. (2017), men and women's mobility is decreasing i.e. they spend about the same amount of time as teachers before becoming superintendents, both sexes appear to have similar stress levels, and mentoring for women is far more common today than in the past. Moreover, women who want to develop in their careers should follow the standards, according to Sandberg (2013). Dealing with society's gender biases is the largest obstacle for women in leadership jobs. Women who lead boldly and directly are frequently erroneously perceived as motivated purely by personal gain however, when men lead, they're respected. This needs more time socializing, especially with other women in comparable roles or further up the organizational ladder. In addition, women must navigate a labyrinth and a glass ceiling to achieve their ambitions. Under pressure, women work harder to prove they can and feel pleased of their achievements.

Women leaders are influenced by various things. Hoch (2014) states that values, leadership skills, and positive role models shape a woman's leadership perspectives. Professional working women considered themselves "clever" as children, with education being the sphere in which they felt most empowered to take the lead. In addition, Perez (2021) finds that most female administrator-educators use a combination of Democratic and Delegation or Free Reign styles of leadership, which is acceptable in a democratic country like the Philippines and in public institutions like the Department of Education. Further, Shetty (2018) highlights that women in leadership positions are praised for their eloquence and wit, but often criticized for using too many words and complex sentences. As seen by many and viewed as a fundamental gender difference, women naturally use more words when transmitting messages, diluting the content. Shetty (2018) mentioned in her study that reducing the number of words used in conversations and emails by 25% had a positive effect on women.

According to Blommaert, Meuleman, Leenheer, and Butkevica, (2019) Despite the fact that women strive for advancement and make up the vast majority of educators working in public schools, they do not hold a significant number of positions in education that involve decision-making, administration, or supervision. There is a significant gap between the number of men and women in positions of authority at the highest levels. Heyi and Golga (2022) found that female executives in male-dominated workplaces are more likely to strive for excellence. Female administrators polled their workers to gauge morale in the wake of a change to a female head of department. In Odum's (2010) study, women school leaders faced some hurdles. He said a few superintendents have reported that female employees are still discriminated against in the workplace despite gender discrimination regulations. Often, this bias shows up during the hiring process, when potential employers worry that a woman who applies for a job asks for time off to care for a child or an elderly relative. Women in positions of leadership, teaching, and administration have been shown in the past to face unique challenges, including heavy and unmanageable workloads, insufficient administrative support, and persistent tensions between their professional and personal lives.

In Ormoc City Division – Eighth District, there are seven schools headed by male school heads and five schools are headed by female school heads. According to the study conducted by Heyi and Golga (2022), female executives working in male-dominated

environments exhibit a greater tendency towards pursuing excellence. The female administrators conducted a survey among their subordinates to assess the level of morale subsequent to the appointment of a female department head. Chigozie's (2010) research revealed that female educational administrators encountered multiple challenges. According to his statement, a number of superintendents have indicated that gender discrimination regulations have not fully eliminated workplace discrimination against female employees. Frequently, this partiality manifests itself in the recruitment phase, where prospective employers express concern that a female applicant may request leave to attend to childcare or eldercare responsibilities. Historically, women occupying leadership, teaching, and administrative roles have encountered distinct challenges such as excessive and overwhelming workloads, inadequate administrative assistance, and ongoing conflicts between their professional and personal spheres.

Thus, the personal experiences of these women school heads in managing the school would be an appropriate topic in this study. It is possible that an exploration into the positive and negative experiences of women who hold leadership positions in schools could result in the production of useful data and the identification of trends that could aid in the design of programs and policies tailored to meet the needs of women school heads.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this research was to explore the lived experiences of female school heads in the Ormoc City Division-Eighth District in relation to their leadership roles. The study aimed to ascertain the varied experiences that female school heads encountered within the framework of current trends in education. Eagly and Carli (2007) and Wakefield (2017) used the Leadership Labyrinth model and Feminist Leadership Framework to understand why women school heads have difficulty in leading. Gender differences and human capital are some of the explanations for the gender pay gap.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a transcendental qualitative phenomenological research design by Husserl as explained by Sheehan (2014). Husserl essentially established transcendental phenomenology (TPh), a philosophical approach to qualitative research methodology that seeks to explain human experience (Moustakas, 1994). This study enabled me to concentrate on women school heads experiences while eliminating intentional researcher bias.

Sampling Method

This study was conducted in Ormoc City Division District Eight, Ormoc City, Leyte. Ormoc City District Eight office was located at Brgy. Dolores, Ormoc City, Leyte. There were twelve elementary schools and two high schools that belong in District Eight, Ormoc City Division namely, Luna Elementary School, Magaswe Elementary School, Dolores Elementary School, Bagong Elementary School, Milagro Elementary School, Cabaon-an Elementary School, Nueva Vista Elementary School, Lake Danao Integrated School, Cambantog Primary School, Gaas Integrated School, Maglahug Elementary School, Liberty Elementary School and Dolores National High School. These schools are located at about five to fifteen kilometers away from the city proper of Ormoc. The means of public transportation from the city was tricycle. However, roads are also passable for private vehicles.

Ormoc City District Eight consists twelve schools. There are twelve school heads in the said district. Seven schools are headed by men school heads and five schools are headed by women school heads.

This study involved four women school heads. They were selected on purpose using purposive sampling. Four participants were selected from the different schools in District Eight, Ormoc City Division i.e. school heads from all elementary and secondary schools in District Eight, Ormoc City Division which were the target population in the selection of participants. The study required participation from all identified participants. On the other hand, the selection method did not take into consideration either the age of the participants or the number of years they have been in the school as school heads.

Research Instruments

A semi-structured guide questions for interview with open-ended questions was used in this study. This instrument is suitable for this type of inquiry. According to Creswell (2014), in-depth interviews is a qualitative research technique comprised of predefined open-ended questions that allow participants to freely explore their understandings and thoughts. It will assist the researcher to understand and analyze the opinions of the participants. Furthermore, Moustakas (1994) believes that informal interviews with open-ended questions are the most effective for qualitative phenomenological research. I customized the interview questions to the comprehension levels of the interviewees. I used simple concepts and languages so that participants may comprehend and adequately communicate their understanding. Field notes, were recorded in a gnomonic, shortened form, contain reconstructions of events, observations, and discussions that occurred in the field. When performing qualitative research, field notes are strongly advised by Moustakas (1994) as a means of documenting the required contextual information.

Data Collection

A letter of communication was sent to the Franciscan College of the Immaculate Conception Dean of the Graduate School, Schools Division Superintendent of Ormoc City Division, Public Schools Division Supervisor of Ormoc City District Eight and to the school principal of Milagro Elementary School asking permission to conduct the study. After securing the permits, consent form was given to the participants who were invited via phone call, and Facebook messenger. Right after the approval of the conduct of the study, an interview was conducted face-to-face with time and location determined by the participants. An audio and video recording using an android phone were utilized to gain clearer and more accurate responses from the participants.

A developed and evaluated open-ended questions were used during the interview. All the participants were able to freely express their experiences using the different languages they were comfortable. Right after the interview, both parties agreed that all information will be kept and stored in a protected file and treated as confidential. The transcription of recorded data followed immediately right after all the information was collected from the participants. Information was transcribed in Microsoft Word and copies of the transcribed data were sent to the participants for them to have time checking the accuracy of their statements. A debriefing was also conducted after the interview. Finally, after presenting the data to the committee, the raw data was deleted as agreed on the consent form.

Data Analysis Procedure

First was listening to the audio recording and transcribing it and followed by making initial coding of the data. Right after, emergent themes were developed by coding relevant phrases and statements in the transcriptions and in the notes and made them into themes. Next step was to split, combine the coded phrases and statements and attained the desired themes. After generating the desired themes, the last step was taking interpretations into a deeper level and generated one main theme. Right after, a dendrogram of the participants' responses was constructed showing the main themes and sub themes that were generated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from the study established three major themes which were interpreted from the lived experiences of the women school heads in Ormoc City Division-Eighth District. These themes are the following: first is the Eventful Encounters which has six sub-themes namely: Ambivalent Emotions, Bright Outlook Towards Work, Support from Stakeholders, Support System of Family, Exceptional Leadership and Success in Leadership, second is the Sense of Honor which has six sub-themes namely: Equality in the Workplace, Being Resourceful, Collaboration and Cooperation in Work, Discernment in Decision Making, Good Working Relationship, and Respect in the Workplace, lastly is the Life is A Highway which has five sub-themes namely: A Seesaw Partnership, The Juggler, The Journey is a Weight on my Shoulder, A Tortoise Under its Shell, and The Divergent.

EVENTFUL ENCOUNTERS

Eventful Encounters are experiences that are difficult to forget. Women school heads, who were the participants in the study have eventful encounters in leading a certain school. Women school heads' responses from their lived experiences under this theme unveiled six sub-themes namely: Ambivalent Emotions, Bright Outlook Towards Work, Support from Stakeholders, Support System of Family, Exceptional Leadership and Success in Leadership.

Ambivalent Emotions. Based from the responses of the participants, they already have a lot of experiences. Some women school heads shared that they have mixed emotions experiences like; sad, disappointing, frustrating, discouraging, and fearful experiences. But they also have experienced beautiful, exciting, positive, happy, and inspiring experiences. Women school heads in Ormoc City Division-Eighth District also shared that they are thankful for they have the best experiences of being school heads. It was also shared by some of the participants that relying on prayers and having faith in God made the good results of their decisions for the betterment of the students and the school as a whole.

This study is congruent to the study of Kruse (2021), female leaders are more likely to display positive emotions than their male counterparts. This may be due, in part, to the fact that women believe they must continue to disprove the notion that they are "too emotional" to be successful leaders. Women school heads considered ambivalent emotions as their eventful experience.

Bright Outlook Towards Work. A bright outlook helped the participants cope better under stressful situations at work and served as a guide to leading positive life. According to Wormley (2017), maintaining a positive attitude through the ups and downs is important to every aspect of life: your social status, your work, your health and your relationships. It is all in the attitude that we able to make things in a better situation. A positive attitude always makes a way to a better result of what you are doing and planning, and it will lead you to a better future indeed. This finding is supported with the study of Johnson et al. (2018) who point adopting a positive and supportive approach while working with subordinates significantly contributed to making their daily tasks easier and reduced the burden of heavy workloads.

Support from Stakeholders. These results build on existing body of evidence that women school heads got the greater support from stakeholders in the school they lead. Donation of concrete classrooms, donation of temporary classrooms, repair materials, maneuvers, and physical support from the private and public stakeholders were met. James et al. (2019) highlight that stakeholders, including teachers, parents, students, and administrators, play a crucial role in shaping the education system.

Support System of Family. A study conducted by Johnson et al. (2017) found that individuals who have strong familial support systems experience reduced levels of stress and increased emotional stability. The study highlighted how the presence of caring and understanding family members can act as a buffer against the challenges and adversities of life, ultimately aiding in effective coping strategies during difficult times.

Furthermore, another study by Williams and Smith (2019) corroborated these findings, suggesting that family support plays a crucial role in fostering resilience and promoting mental well-being.

Exceptional Leadership. It is the ability to foster and develop the love, trust and respect from others that is needed to inspire them to both listen and follow you anywhere. This type of leadership involves the extraordinary roles of school heads. Moreover, research conducted by Johnson and Williams (2019) investigate the impact of leadership qualities such as knowledge, courage, and empathy, and found that these attributes were positively associated with the overall effectiveness of women school heads in their respective schools.

Success in Leadership. Through effective leadership, there comes success, which is the common goal of the school. There are many successes in the school leadership that women school heads may achieve together with their subordinates and the people around them. Several studies have highlighted the significance of perseverance, delegation, and trust as essential qualities for women school leaders to achieve success in their roles. Lee et al. (2017) examine the leadership traits of successful women school principals and found that perseverance and determination were key factors in overcoming challenges and achieving positive outcomes for their schools.

Figure 1. Eventful Encounters

SENSE OF HONOR

When recalling and describing the experiences and information shared by the participants during the interview, they have shown characters that secured the possible development of heart, mind, body, and a fruitful channelization of life-energy that was very useful for every woman school head in leading a school.

Equality in the Workplace. Therefore, to be treated equal with everybody is one of the things that anyone would be thankful for. Women school heads experienced equal treatment in the workplace especially to their fellow school heads. In connection with these, a study by Johnson et al. (2018) investigate the impact of workplace equality initiatives and found that organizations that actively promoted equality and diversity experienced higher levels of employee satisfaction, reduced conflicts, and improved overall team performance.

Being Resourceful. School leaders play a critical role in shaping the educational environment and ensuring optimal outcomes for students, teachers, and the school community. One of the key responsibilities of effective school leaders is the strategic management of resources to support the school's mission and goals. Moreover, Hitt and Tucker (2016) highlight the importance of networking and collaboration in resourcefulness. School leaders who actively engage with other educational leaders, community organizations, and businesses are more likely to gain access to additional resources and support, thereby expanding their capacity to address various needs within the school.

Collaboration and Cooperation in Work. Collaboration was also a mark of cooperation in the workplace. It should be a part of any team that aimed to be successful. Based on the lived experiences that the women school heads in Ormoc City Division-Eighth District shared during the interview, many factors of cooperation have helped them get through in the daily workloads. Johnson and Richards (2017) suggests that implementing distributed leadership practices can be beneficial for promoting school improvement and enhancing student outcomes.

Discernment in Decision Making. Spirituality, often rooted in religious or philosophical beliefs, is a multifaceted aspect of human life that can profoundly influence decision-making processes. Studies in the fields of psychology and organizational behavior have extensively examined the connection between spirituality and decision-making, as well as the role of faith in guiding individuals towards making better choices.

The study of Khoshakhlagh & Mohammadi (2016) examines how spiritual intelligence is related to ethical decision-making, which is a subset of decision-making in a broader context. While this study doesn't focus exclusively on the overall relationship between spiritual intelligence and decision-making, it provides insights into the connection between spiritual intelligence and a specific aspect of decision-making.

Good Working Relationship. A good work relationship requires trust, respect, self-awareness, inclusion, and open communication. A workplace should practice being patient and share strengths with colleagues and subordinates to have a good working relationship. Bascia (2020) pointed out when women school heads emphasize the significance of good relationships and a harmonious workplace, it encourages teacher collaboration and teamwork. Positive relationships among staff members promote effective communication, cooperation, and mutual support, which, in turn, can lead to improved teaching practices and student outcomes.

Respect in the Workplace. Showing *respect* to colleagues encourages innovative thinking and increased productivity as employees know that their contributions are valued. As specified by Herryty (2023), respect is the feeling of regarding someone well for their qualities or traits, but respect can also be the action of treating people with appreciation and dignity.

Figure 2. Sense of Honor

LIFE IS A HIGHWAY

Women's participation in educational leadership has been revitalized since the middle of the twentieth century. Their prominent representation and participation have presented them with challenges in positions of authority, such as primary and secondary school leadership. It is well-documented that women face challenges or obstacles in breaking into school administration (Hennig & Jardin, 1977; Zirkel & Gluckerman, 1984; Swiderski, 1988; Mauer, 1994; Thomas, 1997). In recent years, there has been an increase in both the proportion of women entering the field of school administration and the number of principals leaving their positions.

A Seesaw Partnership. This talks about the challenges experienced by women school heads in partnership with stakeholders. Stakeholders have the significant responsibility of leading and supporting the learners and in creating an enjoyable environment so that the latter's potential and self-confidence can develop well. Furthermore, a research by Smyth (2018) explores the importance of community engagement in the educational process. It suggests that school leaders collaborating with local stakeholders, including government authorities, community members, and NGOs, can pool resources and expertise to overcome challenges and enhance educational opportunities for students.

The Juggler. As a women school head, it is necessary to keep the bind with colleagues and subordinates, show them importance and respect to keep the team working on the common goals. The statement about women school heads finding better strategies through overcoming challenges in their leadership aligns with the broader literature on leadership development and the characteristics of effective leaders. Moreover, research by Smith and Lee (2021) explores the attributes of successful leaders, which include being organized and focused. A good leader, as Tanja Sternbauer states, keeps the team on track and avoids delays through efficient planning, prioritization, and effective time management.

The Journey is a Weight on my Shoulder. In the context of transportation difficulties, women school heads may have learned to navigate through such obstacles, becoming more resilient and resourceful in finding alternative solutions. Moreover, the study by Lee et al. (2022) explores the impact of transportation on employee performance. As Sufiyan Afzal (2022) states, a hassle-free daily commute can improve employee performance and contribute to overall organizational growth.

A Tortoise under its Shell. Every employee will always prefer to work in a safe place. The statement highlights the significance of workplace safety in fostering peace of mind, which, in turn, can lead to improved work performance. A study by Huang et al. (2019) examined the impact of workplace safety on employee performance. The research found that employees who perceived their workplace to be safe reported higher job satisfaction, reduced stress levels, and improved job performance compared to those in less safe work environments.

The Divergent. Based from the responses of the participants, it is in factions of teachers that gossips arise, negative feedback to colleagues come out that lead to misunderstandings in the workflow. The study by Hoy and Tarter (2016) suggests that addressing factionalism and promoting a positive school culture are essential for effective school leadership. School heads need to actively engage in building a cohesive and supportive work environment to align teachers towards common goals and improve overall school performance.

Figure 3. LIFE IS A HIGHWAY

Significant Statements

**Sub-Themes
Developed**

**Theme
Developed**

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Lived experiences of women school heads in Ormoc City Division - Eighth District are the experiences that may help make them even better school heads. Experiences can transform woman to a wiser and stronger version of herself. The sense of honor secured the fullest possible development of the mind, body, and heart and contribute to the learning opportunity and positive outcomes that provides a different perspective for continuing professional development as women school heads in addressing the problems encountered in school.

The conclusions in the study served as basis to come up with some recommendations. This study recommends to 1. Widen the scope of participants to investigate the impact of culture in the management of women school heads to gain a more comprehensive understanding of how culture affects women school heads' management experiences, the study should include a diverse and representative sample of participants from various cultural backgrounds and geographic regions and by incorporating voices from different cultural contexts. 2. Conduct a comparative study on lived experiences between men and women school heads because through conducting a comparative study between male and female school heads can shed light on gender-specific challenges and disparities in leadership experiences and by analyzing the similarities and differences between the two groups, the research can highlight potential areas where gender biases and cultural factors may play a significant role. 3. Adopt the proposed action plans for women school heads.

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